

Application of 10 kg BGA/ha significantly increased the 1981 rice yield over the no-fertilizer, no-BGA control at the Government Farm in Regza and Sar-

kanda Bilaspur (Table 2). Combining 20 kg N and 10 kg BGA/ha caused a significant yield increase over 20 kg N/ha alone at Regza.

BGA did not develop spontaneously in the experimental fields. Scanty green algae biomass was noticed on N-fertilized plots. □

Optimum transplanting time for rice: an agrometeorological approach

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To maximize rice grain yield, it is necessary to determine optimum planting date. We used grain yield pattern and water and energy use efficiencies to determine correct planting date.

Our experiment at Raipur (21°14'N, 81°39'E) in the 1981 monsoon season was on clay loam with pH 6.5. Asha (R-35-2752), a dwarf indica, was planted in 3 replications at 10- × 20-cm spacing on 10 dates at 10-day intervals between 1 Jun and 30 Aug. Fertilizer was applied at 100 kg N, 26 kg P, and 33 kg K/ha. Net radiation and potential evapotranspiration values were estimated by Penman's equation and meteorological parameters recorded at the Agricultural Meteorology Observatory.

Phenological data, grain yield, yield-contributing characters, and total dry matter production are shown in the table. Yield-contributing characters varied little among transplanting dates, but there was a marked difference in grain yield pattern (see figure). Yield pattern and duration from sowing to 50% flowering indicated that transplanting between 11 and 21 Jul will produce optimum yields.

Water use efficiency (kg/ha per mm of

evapotranspiration) for grain yield was highest for rice transplanted between 11 and 31 Jul (see table). Water use efficiency for dry matter production was highest between 11 and 21 Jul.

Energy use efficiency did not vary significantly, but a definite relation existed between net accumulated radiation from flowering to maturity and grain yield pattern. Higher radiation produced higher yields. □

Accumulated evapotranspiration during different physiological stages, yield contributing characters, and water use efficiency of rice crops.

Transplanting date	Accumulated evapotranspiration (mm)			Total	Effective tillers/hill	Sound grains /panicle	Dry matter (t/ha)	Grain yield (t/ha)	Water use efficiency for	
	Sowing to planting	Planting to 50% flowering	50% flowering to maturity						Grain yield (kg/ha per mm)	Dry matter (kg/ha per mm)
1.6.81	206	349	82	641	6.9	82	11.5	2.7	4.2	17.9
11.6.81	221	310	86	614	7.2	82	13.3	2.6	4.2	21.6
21.6.81	225	270	92	587	6.6	81	13.4	3.0	5.0	22.9
1.7.81	176	258	98	532	7.2	83	13.3	3.4	6.5	25.1
11.7.81	139	244	115	500	7.6	92	11.9	3.8	7.6	25.5
21.7.81	99	250	119	468	7.9	94	12.6	4.0	8.6	26.9
31.7.81	108	252	130	489	6.9	92	9.8	3.8	7.7	20.0
10.8.81	98	267	107	472	5.6	88	8.0	3.5	7.3	16.9
20.8.81	106	250	97	453	5.4	68	7.4	3.1	6.9	16.3
30.8.81	107	229	86	422	4.4	59	7.0	3.1	7.3	16.6

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